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**A Preliminary Study on Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs)
from Heating Empty Nonstick Pans**

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Abstract

In recent years, preheating (empty heating) has been considered to be an incorrect application of non-stick pans, and the practice is usually warned against on newly purchased non-stick pans' labels. This is because non-stick pan coatings may emit toxic volatile organic compounds (VOCs) into the atmosphere when over-heated. However, the public awareness of this hazard is extremely low. The reason lies in the fact that most research in this regard was conducted within non-stick pan manufactories or environmental working groups. In addition, very few researches were published in peer-reviewed journals. The purpose of this study is to develop a convenient method to collect and analyze VOCs emitted from heating pans in a real-life-simulation setting, which in the future can be adopted in field research. It was hypothesized that heating a non-stick pan with water for five minutes will emit less potentially toxic fumes than heating empty. A Solid Phase Micro-extraction (SPME) fiber was used to collect the emitted VOCs, and was then desorbed into a Gas Chromatograph-Mass Spectrometer to analyze its components. Three pans of the same model were tested, forming three trials. The average relative peak areas of one potentially toxic VOC detected, benzoic acid, was 10,570,370 (84.7ng) when heating with water compared to 18,658,261 (139.3ng) when heating without water, a 64% increase when heating dry. The research result confirmed the hypothesis and it will help design large scale field research in the future as well as raising public cautions against preheating non-stick pans.

Keywords: Volatile Organic Compounds, Empty Nonstick Pans, Non-stick Pan Coatings

Basic Introduction and Conceptual Framework

Current Situation

Research done by Galizzi and Venturini (2012) in recent years has demonstrated that many food markets have adopted food sampling services to promote sales and enhance the customer's shopping experience (Figure 1). While this service may increase customers' shopping pleasure, it may expose the public to uninvestigated health hazards. For example, it is typical for a food sampling representative to heat an empty non-stick pan on medium to high, which is generally 162°C to 343°C (Smart Kitchen, 2011), while preparing food within close proximity of waiting customers several times throughout the day. The constant preheating results in the release of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) indoors coupled with several other factors that magnify the risk of releasing VOCs when using non-stick pans in these establishments. These factors include using an over-aged non-stick pan, and the lack of an adequate ventilation system. Though the Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) does not have standards regarding indoor air quality (IAQ) (OSHA, 2011), OSHA does require that employers provide a safe workplace that does not have any known hazards. VOCs, such as those released through the heating of non-stick pans, are listed as a common IAQ contaminant by OSHA and so should still be monitored and minimized in an effort to maintain safe working conditions.

Figure 1. Supermarket Employee Preparing Food in Close Proximity to Customers. Retrieved from <http://supermarketnews.com/>

Potential Dangers from Overheating Non-stick Pan Coatings

Non-stick pan coatings have been reported to emit various toxic fumes into the atmosphere when over-heated, usually above 260 °C (Houlihan, Thayer, & Klein, 2003, Sinclair, et al., 2007). These toxic VOCs can cause severe lung damage and have been found to cause deaths in birds, and can result in "flu-like" symptoms in humans including headache and chills according to one study (Houlihan, Thayer, & White, 2003). With the advanced heating technologies currently available, non-stick pan coatings can reach the break-down point (348 °C) in as little as 5 minutes when heated empty (preheated) (Houlihan, Thayer, & Klein, 2003). This breakdown point is the reason why non-stick pan manufacturers have issued warning labels against preheating non-stick pans when empty. According to the DuPont chemical industry company, the first and largest manufacturer of non-stick cookware with polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE/Teflon) non-stick coatings have a recommended maximum use temperature of 260 °C, which could be easily reached if non-stick pans were left empty on a hot burner. In 2003 the Environmental Working Group (EWG) reported that non-stick coatings "could reach 700 degrees Fahrenheit (371 °C) in as little as 3 to 5 minutes, releasing 15 toxic gases and chemicals, including two carcinogens" (Houlihan, et al., 2003). In early 2006, the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) asked eight American companies, including DuPont, maker of Teflon-brand non-stick cookware, to work towards the elimination of certain harmful toxins by 2015.

Noted by the manufacturers, the non-stick pans are safe to use as long as the temperatures do not exceed 500°F (i.e. 260 °C), the pans are not used for longer than three to five years, and that cooking is done under a good ventilation unit (Wolke, 2008). However, food sample services in supermarkets may not have sufficient engineering controls such as adequate ventilation to remove toxic VOCs released during food preparation exercises, special precautions to prevent over-heating

of the non-stick pans used, or non-stick pan replacements at recommended intervals. Also, out of 50 meal recipes collected at one local supermarket over a two-month-period, at least 34 (68%) of the recipes specifically instruct users to "preheat a large, non-stick sauté pan on medium-high 2-3 minutes" before adding any ingredients to the pan. With approximately 2000 recipes published by one supermarket chain online, at this rate there would be nearly 1400 recipes with instructions to preheat a non-stick pan (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Supermarket Menus Instructing Preheating Non-stick Pans.

Strong Research Need: Low Public Awareness

One of the reasons for the low public awareness of this important usage guidance for non-stick pans may be the lack of published research in this regard. Although EWG and manufacturers may have conducted many studies, few of them are published on peer-reviewed journals. A literature search on the internet and library database only generates Houlihan, et al. (2003) and Sinclair et al. (2007) directly addressing non-stick pans. Houlihan, et al. (2003) is a brief report stating that “heated Teflon pans can turn toxic faster than DuPont claims,” without describing the actual research method. In Sinclair et al. (2007), air is collected through resin tubes

connected to a vacuum pump, which may be impractically intrusive in field research. To raise public awareness, larger scale field research needs to be conducted.

Research Purpose and Tentative Choices

The purpose of this study was to preliminarily investigate the VOCs that would be released from non-stick pans under similar conditions that would be used in the public waiting area of a supermarket. Because this study is preliminary, the goal it sets to achieve is to find a relatively economical and efficient method to detect VOCs that can be used in large scale field research in the future. There are three common methods available in the lab: The first is to place a sponge near the heated pans for a specific time period. Afterwards, the sponge is soaked in solutions and the analytes in the solution are analyzed through Liquid Chromatography. However, after several trials, this method was rejected because the sponge may not be absorbent enough to catch VOCs. The second method is to use a Solid Phase Micro-Extractor (SPME) fiber coated with Polydimethylsiloxane directly to collect emits from heating pans and then analyze the collections with Liquid Chromatography techniques. However, because it is unknown if the emits would be non-polar enough to be absorbed by Polydimethylsiloxane coating, this method was also rejected. Finally, we decided to use a SPME coated with divenylbenzene on carboxen with polydimethylsiloxane (DVB/CAR/PDMS), which is suitable to collect a larger range of analytes, polar and non-polar. After collecting analytes, the SPME are inserted into Gas Chromatograph-Mass Spectrometer (GC-MS) and peaks are analyzed to identify the VOCs. The advantages of SPME collection is that it is fast and simple because extraction does not involve solvents. Also, it is practical for potential large scale field research because on-site sampling can be performed without an analytical instrument present, and the samples can be analyzed days later without significant loss of analytes.

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) is an analytical technique used to separate compounds using vaporization (GC) and determine the amount and type of chemicals

present using mass-to-charge ratios (MS). Over the years, the cost of a GC-MS has decreased significantly, and they have become commonly used for chemical warfare agent detection and forensics for substance identification. The setback to using gas chromatography is that the compounds analyzed must be volatile in order to vaporize in the column, but there may be some compounds emitted by non-stick pan coatings that are not volatile enough to be detected. Under these circumstances, Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry could have given a better overall analysis. However, due to financial limitations, a Liquid Chromatograph could not be secured. Because this study is mainly concerned with potential volatile emits in public area, not using a Liquid Chromatograph is acceptable.

Research Design and Methodology

The collection and analysis method proposed here is an economical and efficient method that can be used in large and comprehensive experiments with many more variables considered, such as various brands of pans, other incorrect use of non-stick pans, et al.

With the collection and analysis method decided, it is hypothesized that, if non-stick pans are heated empty or containing water, then heating the pans containing water will emit less toxic VOCs into the atmosphere than heating empty pans as water can maintain the overall temperature of the pan until its boiling point (100^o C), greatly diminishing the non-stick coating's chances of reaching the 260^o C breakdown point. This directional hypothesis could be stated as: H1: $\mu_1 < \mu_2$ and the reason of using directional hypothesis was discussed in research question.

Research Question

A one-tailed test is appropriate in situation when empirical research, common sense or previous experiences reveals that the difference is most possibly going in one direction. It is also true with this particular research. As a result, the research question was raised:

RQ: Does heating the pans containing water emit significantly less toxic VOCs into the

atmosphere than heating empty pans?

Brief Design and Materials

Non-stick pans were Joyce Chen Wok 14-inch diameter non-stick pans, purchased from a local supermarket where food sampling is provided and recipes instructing preheating are distributed. Before each trial, like in Sinclair et al. (2007), all pans were washed with commercial dishwashing liquid, rinsed with warm water, and dried with paper towels. The non-stick pans were first heated empty, then with 400ml of deionized water, forming three trials for each condition.

Other materials include: one Bunsen Burner, three clamps and clamp stands to hold the pans over the burner, one electronic temperature gauge, several pairs of gloves, and one timer.

Research Instruments

The study was conducted in a Chemistry lab at Florida International University, under supervision of the lab manager. The lab has an exhaust fume hood as well as the other equipment used in the experiment. Extraction of VOCs was performed using SPME coated with divinylbenzene on carboxen with DVB/CAR/PDMS from Sigma Aldrich corporation, St. Louis, Mo. Temperature of the pans was monitored using a Oakton thermocouple with a K type thermometer probe sourced from Fisher Scientific, Pittsburgh, PA.

Figure 3. Experiment Setup Showing Pan Heated with Bunsen Burner and Sampled with SPME Fiber.

An Agilent 6890N Gas Chromatograph (GC) in split-less mode was used with an HP-5-Mass Spectrometer (MS) ultra-inert column, 30M in length with 0.25 μ m film thickness and 0.25 mm diameter. The GC oven ramp was set at 40 $^{\circ}$ C for 5 minutes, and ramped at 10 $^{\circ}$ C per minute until the temperature was 280 $^{\circ}$ C and held for 1 minute. In addition, an Agilent 5973N Mass Spectrometer was set to a full scan mode with scan range 40-500 AMU with electron impact ionization. A computer connected to the Gas Chromatograph Mass Spectrometer was used to recognize the molecules and print out the data. Mass spectra from the extracted compounds were compared with a NIST 1998 mass spectral library to identify the compounds extracted.

Compound Collection

To prepare for sample collection, six SPME fibers coated with divenylbenzene on carboxen with polydimethylsiloxane (DVB/CAR/PDMS) were labeled with either "Empty 1 to 3" or "Water 1 to 3," in correspondence to its assigned condition for three trials. Each SPME fiber was held over a small opening in the closed lid of the pans using clamps and clamp stands, remaining unexposed until ready to collect VOCs. The small opening was made by unscrewing the screws on the lid. The non-stick pans were placed over a Bunsen burner, and the whole setup was placed under a ventilation hood for safety. Clamps were used to ensure equal height between the flame and pots among all conditions and to hold the SPME fiber in place above the hole in the lid of the pan (Figure 3).

To ensure that the pans were only emitting toxic compounds due to heating, air samples were first collected with a SPME after the pans were washed with soap and water but before they were heated. Then, each non-stick pan was heated empty for five minutes, forming the first three trials, and the temperature of the pan was monitored every minute (Figure 3). The SPME fiber for each sample was injected into the GCMS and the chromatographs were analyzed and recorded. After the three pans were cleaned and cooled to normal room temperature, they were filled with 400 ml of

water and then tested again exactly as in the empty condition.

The compounds were collected and the chromatograph peak areas were recorded and compared between empty and with water heating.

Research Results and Interpretation

As hypothesized, the relative amount of Benzoic Acid increased by 64% in the empty condition when compared to the pan containing water. The average peak area, which is directly related to the concentration of the chemical in the released fumes, was 10,570,370 for pans that were heated with water and 18,658,261 for pans that were being heated empty (dry). Based on the response of spectrometric grade benzoic acid on the GC-MS as seen in Figure 4, this equates to benzoic acid amounts of 84.7ng and 139.3ng respectively. Statistically, their difference is significant with an error chance less than 5 out of 100 ($t_{(2)} = -3.188$, $p < .05$) by a one-tail paired t-Test carried out in Microsoft Excel software (Table 1).

Table 1.

Abundance of Benzoic Acid Emitted (Relative Peak Area)

	Water	Empty
Trial 1	9,515,111	22,637,142
Trial 2	5,697,184	11,822,912
Trial 3	16,498,816	21,514,730
Average	10,570,370	18,658,261
SD	5477590.04	5946129.21
SEM	3162488.08	3432999.3
		df=2
		t= -3.188
		P< .05
Paired Sample t-Test Result (One Tail-Directional)		Sig.: .043

Although other VOCs were detected in the empty condition (Figure 4), these were only identified by mass spectral library match and not confirmed through the use of standard

spectrometric grade reference materials due to funding limitations.

Figure 4. Chromatogram of VOCs Detected from overheated Dry Non-Stick Pan by Headspace-SPME.

On the other hand, although non-stick pans heated with water emitted less toxic fumes than heated empty, with water the pans emitted a greater variety of compounds than without (Table 2).

Table 2

Library Search Summary Report of Other VOCs from Heating Pans with Water

Compound	CAS Number	Percent Quality Match
Benzoic Acid	000065-85-0	91
Benzoic acid, 4-hydroxy-	000099-96-7	81
1,4-Benzenedicarboxylic acid, meth	039379-10-7	94
Benzophenone	000119-61-9	94
9-Octadecenoic acid, (E)	000112-79-8	99
Phenol, 4,4'-(1-methylethylidene)b	000080-05-7	91
1,3-Propanediol, 2-ethyl-2-(hydrox	000077-99-6	78
Phenol, 4-(1-methyl-1-phenylethyl)	000599-64-4	97
Thiophene, 2-(trimethylsilyl)-5-[1000142-86-0	72

As identified by the GC-MS, the only compounds collected before heating the pan were

siloxane compounds, which are degradation products from the SPME fiber.

Discussion and Explanation

In the past decade, large amounts of perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) have been detected in over-heated non-stick pans. Thankfully, as a result of newly improved finishing technologies, it is more difficult to detect PFOA from these pans as coatings are now more resistive limiting the release of VOCs, even on pans coated with polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE). What was always a health problem for PTFE-based cookware, and remains so today, is not actually PFOA itself, but the fact that, when over-heated, non-stick coatings break down and release a variety of VOCs, in addition to PFOA. It is unclear what VOCs may be emitted from the “improved” pans, especially when they are heated empty. Also, there is lack of literature on how to collect VOCs in a real life cooking setting. This study contributed new insights into this reality in several aspects. Each contribution, along with its limitations, is discussed below.

First, the major contribution of this study is that a method has been developed to quickly detect and analyze the VOCs released from a non-stick pan when heated. The use of a SPME to directly collect analytes is a convenient and novel method. The fiber chosen for this experiment was coated with divinylbenzene on carboxen with polydimethyl siloxane (DVB/CAR/PDMS) because it has a mixture of both polar and non-polar chemistries to extract a wide range of compounds. To improve the collection of additional VOCs, the present study could have been conducted with SPME fibers coated with different chemistries. Each would extract different types of compounds, some more polar, some less polar. Other types of SPME fibers that could also be used are Carboxen/Polydimethylsiloxane, which extracts compounds with lower molecular weight, or Polydimethylsiloxane, which extracts non-polar high molecular weight compounds.

The second contribution of this study is that it supported the hypothesis, which was that heating a non-stick pan containing water will emit less toxic VOCs into the atmosphere than heating

an empty non-stick pan. The average peak area of the Benzoic Acid detected was significantly less in "with-water" condition than in "empty" condition. Nonstick pans heated empty emitted more benzoic acid than heated with water. Benzoic acid is a respiratory tract irritant that can cause dyspnea in high concentrations (Bedford & Clarke, 1972; Maki & Takeda, 2000; Nair, 2001). Prolonged skin contact of benzoic acid may also cause dermatitis. Inhalation of benzoic acid over a four week period was shown to cause interstitial fibrosis in rat lungs. Similar compounds, such as acetic acid and decanoic acid, cause chemical conjunctivitis and respiratory tract irritation if inhaled. It can be fatal if it comes into contact with aquatic life (Taber, Nelson, & Northrop, 1999). Besides not pre-heating a non-stick pan, manufacturers and the EWG also recommend not using a pan for too many times until it starts flaking, and always cook under a good ventilation unit. Flaking of the pan coating was observed during our study and resulted in rapid deterioration of the pan followed by increased release of pungent VOCs. As noted, supermarkets prepare foods for sampling several times per day, especially during crowded weekends, without a cooking ventilation system. It is unknown how often those pans are replaced but new pans are not used all the time. Our study showed a 64% increase in at least one toxic fume in heating empty pans, which may actually present a best case scenario because new pans were used under a ventilation hood. Thus, this second contribution of detecting at least one toxic gas is significant and practical. By directly collecting fumes from pans heated under two conditions (wet and dry), the results of this study are more realistic and should be more effective in raising public awareness about the necessary steps required to minimize any potential harmful effects of misusing non-stick pans.

There are three limitations about this second contribution though. First, future studies can seek to determine whether the concentrations are high enough to cause harm (e.g. ≥ 6 mg/kg). Second, other VOCs were detected but their sources and toxicities were not studied due to funding limitations, which warrant further investigations to increase public awareness and improve coating

techniques. Third, the results show that although non-stick pans heated with water emitted less toxic fumes than heated empty, with water the pans emitted a greater variety of compounds than without. This may have been because water, the second most polar molecule, displaced a variety of non-polar compounds through the hole of the pan cover through which the SPME fiber was inserted. This is an interesting phenomenon that can be further investigated in other experiments.

In addition to the limitations directly related to the contributions, several issues with regard to the design of this study warrant discussion. First, for future tests it would be useful to include a third condition to test pans containing oil because oil is used more frequently with non-stick pans and can reach a higher temperature than water. A previous study (Begley, 2005) observed that food oil began to generate smoke at around 190°C, which is still lower than the non-stick coating's breaking temperature. Second, the pans' temperatures in this study were monitored by probing the thermometer onto the external off-center surface of the pan. Although the empty pan's temperature went up faster than the pan with water, the actual temperature inside the pan was not monitored as the pan was covered in an attempt to capture the released VOCs (Figure 3). In future studies, it would be informative to determine a method to also record the pan's internal temperature and graph the temperature increase over time.

One reviewer pointed out that there may be two confounding variables. The first is that pans were washed with soap and heating soap may emit VOCs. In this study the confounding effects of soap is considered minimal for several reasons. First, pans for both conditions were equally washed with soap, so soap's effect, if existent, should not have an impact on the difference between two conditions. Second, all pans were thoroughly rinsed with water and there is barely any soap left. Therefore the results might have been more primarily due to the coating itself. Last, washing the pans with soap is an attempt to imitate the daily use of pans. If soap residues do emit VOCs when being heated, then the combined effects of soap and coating are practically meaningful. Nevertheless,

it would be helpful also to test pans before they were washed with soap.

Likewise, as an attempt to imitate real life use of pans, the lid was kept in the experiment, which may potentially cause another confounding effect to address. The lid is made mostly of glass and stainless-steel, which is highly resistant to heat. Therefore, there is little reason to believe that the lid itself might emit any kind of chemicals when heated by the water vapor or fumes.

Nevertheless, it would be helpful to repeat the study without the lid.

In addition, another limitation is that the sample size was not big enough to provide deep insights into the research considering that larger sample sizes were required for more valid research result.

Conclusion and Insights on Future Research

In summary, to investigate the health hazards related to preheating non-stick pans, this study is only the first laboratory step, simulating the real time situation. This study developed an applicable method and its results confirmed hypothesis, thus warranting further investigation. After more studies are carried out as discussed above, large scale field research needs to be conducted on site. In future research, more variables will be taken into consideration and investigation, including the age of pans, the ventilation level, the cooking temperature, the brands and models of the pans, etc. It may also be necessary to conduct longitudinal research because some health hazards may not show effects immediately.

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